

The rice root nematode in lowland paddies in Kerala, India

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A survey of nematode parasites in the lowland rice areas of Kerala showed the rice root nematode *Hirschmanniella oryzae* in all regions (see map). All 104 soil samples collected at 43 sites were infested; so were the roots of rice planted in the soils. The number of nematodes ranged from 5 to 509/250 ml of soil and was as high as 450/sample of plant roots. Nematode infestation was found in lateritic loam, clayey loam, sandy, and pokkali (saline) soil types. The rice varieties Aswathi, Bharathi, Jaya, Mahoori, Triveni, and Annapoorna were infected. The nematode also infested the lowland weeds *Monochoria vaginalis*, *Fimbristylis miliaria*, *Cyperus iria*, *C. elusoides*, and *Vallisneria spiralis*.

The distribution of the rice root nematode in rice regions of Kerala, India.

Yield loss due to infection by rice root nematode in Triveni, Kerala, India.

Treatment ^a	Nematode population (no.)		Grain yield (kg/plot)	Yield loss (%)
	At planting, in 250 ml soil	At harvest In 250 ml soil In 5 g roots		
Natural field population	11	245	1.54	4.3
100 g infected rice roots added/plot	14	180	1.23	19.2
200 g infected rice roots added/plot	33	836	1.32	13.8
DBCP at 30 liters/ha	0	0	1.53	
E.D. (p=0.05)			0.20	

^a Mean of 6 replicates.

Studies of yield losses in 4-m² field microplots revealed significant reductions in final grain weight with increases in

nematode population in soil and plant roots at harvest (see table). □

Preliminary results of fertilization of upland rice in the Llanos Orientales of Colombia

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Preliminary trials were conducted to investigate the response to N, P, and K applications of upland rice in two soils of the Llanos Orientales of Colombia. Two experiments were on savanna soils (Oxisols), which are extremely acid (pH 3.9), and have low fertility and are high in exchangeable aluminum. Three experiments were on river-bottom soils (Entisols) without aluminum, with a medium-high fertility level and pH higher than 5.5.

The yields on the savanna soils were low because of low soil fertility and high aluminum toxicity, and because the rice variety planted (IR8) is susceptible to such adverse soil conditions. Yields were more than doubled by the application of 75 kg P₂O₅/ha, but no response was obtained from nitrogen (Fig. 1).

Statistical analysis of data from the river bottom experiments showed optimum yields of about 6 t/ha from application of 70 kg/ha of nitrogen on variety Cica 8 (Fig. 2).

No response to P or K was observed in these experiments because the soil

1. Response of upland rice (variety IR8) to N and P₂O₅ in Oxisols of the Llanos Orientales, Colombia. Mean of two locations.

2. Calculated yields of upland rice (variety CICA 8) with different N levels.

content was adequate, especially for K (P Bray II = 15.7 ppm; K = 0.72 meq/100 g soil).

The best method of applying nitrogen was 3 equal split applications at 30, 50,

and 70 days after germination.

Sowing upland rice in savanna soils is not recommended because the varieties lack tolerance for excessive exchangeable aluminum, the most limiting factor in those soils. □

Effect of time of burying of Dhaincha *Sesbania aculeata* on nitrogen economy in paddy

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The crop recovers only about 15 to 40% of applied nitrogen in submerged paddy soils. The recent increase in paddy cultivation in nontraditional, light-textured soils in northeastern India has further aggravated the problem. It is important to develop a technology to increase the efficiency of nitrogen utilization and to conserve the nitrogen harnessed through green manure.

An experiment to test the relationship of Dhaincha (*Sesbania*) green manure to nitrogen economy was initiated at the PAU farm, Ludhiana, in 1977 kharif.

Effect on paddy yield of different times of burying Dhaincha.^a Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana, India.

Days buried before puddling	Grain yield (t/ha)				Av.
	No N	60 kg N/ha	90 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha	
Fallow	2.4	4.7	5.2	5.5	4.5
20	4.2	5.8	5.7	5.5	5.3
10	5.0	5.5	5.4	5.6	5.4
0	5.7	5.6	5.6	6.2	5.1
Av.	4.1	5.4	5.5	5.7	

^aC.D. at 5% for N level: 5.7; C.D. for dates: 5.7; C.D. for dates × N level: 6.1

PAU presently recommends the burying of green manure about 2 weeks before transplanting paddy — which means that Dhaincha should be sown by the second or third week of April, when farmers are busy with the rabi harvest and postharvest operations. Because farmers are reluctant to include green manure in their cropping pattern, an experiment to determine the optimum time to bury Dhaincha without adversely affecting paddy yield was designed. (Dhaincha buried immediately before transplanting was thought to adversely affect crop growth because of nitrogen immobilization, low Eh value, and

formation of organic acid on higher partial CO₂ pressure.) But it was more beneficial to bury Dhaincha at puddling than at 20 or 10 days before puddling (see table). Interestingly, it saved 120 kg N/ha. The recommended method saved only 60 kg N/ha. The new technique makes conservation of 100% more nitrogen possible, and gives farmers 15 more days to plan their Dhaincha sowing during the busy season.

The experiment was repeated in 1978 at the PAU farm and in farmers' fields in Ludhiana district. Effects on crop growth seem similar. Investigations will be reported. □

Effects of leaf area index and spacing on the productivity of Pankaj

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The longduration variety Pankaj (a selection of IR5) was transplanted at the Agricultural Research Institute, Patna, in the 1977 kharif using a strip-plot design with three replications. Two rates of nitrogen — N₁ (50 kg N/ha) and N₂, (100 kg N/ha) — and five spacings — S₁ (10 × 10 cm), S₂ (15 × 15 cm), S₃ (20 × 20 cm), S₄ (25 × 25 cm), and S₅ (30 × 30 cm) — were used. Basal treatments of superphosphate and muriate were used for all plots at 60 kg P₂O₅/ha and 40 kg K₂O/ha. The leaf area index (LAI) was recorded at five stages: maximum tillering, panicle initiation, ear emergence, dough, and ripening. The final yield was recorded.

Grain yield in relation to leaf area index and plant spacing at the Agricultural Research Institute, Patna, India.

Treatment ^a	Leaf area index					Yield (t/ha)
	Maximum tillering	Panicle initiation	Ear emergence	Dough	Ripening	
N ₁ S ₁	3.0	4.2	9.4	9.2	7.8	5.9
N ₂ S ₁	3.5	1.3	9.7	8.9	8.2	5.6
N ₁ S ₂	3.9	3.7	11.1	6.0	7.1	6.3
N ₂ S ₂	4.3	3.4	7.4	9.0	5.2	6.3
N ₁ S ₃	1.4	2.4	5.7	6.7	4.1	5.8
N ₂ S ₃	1.0	3.3	5.6	5.5	3.4	6.6
N ₁ S ₄	1.8	3.7	4.7	5.3	3.9	5.8
N ₂ S ₄	1.8	3.2	4.9	5.2	3.9	6.1
N ₁ S ₅	0.7	2.1	3.5	4.9	2.6	4.1
N ₂ S ₅	1.0	2.2	3.2	4.9	2.5	4.9

^aN₁ = 50 kg N/ha, N₂ = 100 kg N/ha, S₁ = 10 × 10 cm, S₂, = 15 × 15 cm, S₃, = 20 × 20 cm, S₄, = 25 × 25 cm, S₅, = 30 × 30 cm.

The results show that the LAI at ear emergence and at the dough stage was related to yield. The LAI was visibly higher in the close spacing than in the wide spacing.

Pankaj yielded higher at 15- × 15-cm

spacing with 50 kg N/ha and at 20 × 20 cm with 100 kg N/ha. Spacings greater than 25 cm between plants adversely affected yields. There was no yield response to the second 50 kg N/ha. □